

TYOLOGY OF HYPOTAXEME WITH ADVERBIAL CLAUSE OF CAUSALITY AND ITS CONSTANT FEATURES IN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the typology of a hypotaxeme(a complex sentence) with an adverbial clause of causality and its constant features in more than 80 languages of the world, which allowed the author to reveal certain typological characteristics of the mentioned hypotaxeme, mainly its universal, frequental and implicative laws of structural-semantic organization and functional usage.

Keywords: hypotaxeme, adverbial clause of causality, constant features, universal, frequental and implicative features, structural-semantic organization, functional usage.

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Modern world linguistics is constantly evolving, its new directions are also emerging, however, one of its ancient directions is linguistic typology, which studies the languages of the world in order to identify, establish and describe their common (universal) and distinctive(private) features by possible means and ways of verbalization of certain cognitive-conceptual semantics in various world.languages.

Typological analysis has established that out of 102 languages subjected to typological studies, 83 of them have hypotaxemes¹⁰⁴ with an adverbial component of causality (HPT with AK of causality) as a really existing and functioning type of syntactic unit, including in English, Uzbek and Russian. This indicates that in the remaining 9 languages, along with HPT with AK of causality, there coexist monotaxemes with an adverbial causality part of a sentence.

In the overwhelming majority of languages, namely, in 83 of them, subordinators serve as means of syntactic connection between the components of HPT with AK of causality. So, in 74 languages, the latter are represented by conjunctions, i.e. connectors , and in 9 of them this function is performed by such means as connectors. (see: table 2), for example:

in English: It would have been better than Stresa because there are

¹⁰⁴For detailed information on “hypotaxeme” as a subtype of “polytaxeme” see: Khoshimov G.M. Typology of complex sentences in languages of different systems, Tashkent, “Fan”, 1991, 107; Khoshimov G.M.: Principles and methods of typological comparison of composite sentences, Andijzhan, “Khayot”. 2017. 156 p.

fewer people at Pallanza (E.Hemingway. A Farewell to Arms, 99);
 in Uzbek: Biz sizni chaqirtirib o'tirmadik, chunki siz o'ushanda uyingizda
 yo'q edingiz (Andijonnoma, 1999, No. 11, 4);
 in Russian: Он и сам это чувствовал, а потому изо всех сил старался
 придать своему голосу мягкость и нежность
 (А.П.Чехов, Рассказы, 101).

At the same time, it should be noted that in 57 languages studied, the syntactic connection between the clauses of the HPT with AC of causality is carried out by subordinators-conjunctions.

table 2

№	Types of means of syntactic connection Languages	AC of causality	Quantity of means of syntactic connection	conjunctions	conjunctions	postpositions	prepositions	particles	Zero means of syntactic connection	Affixes	Borrowed means of connection	Dominating means of connection	The position of the means of connection in relation to the adverbial component				Position of the adverbial component in relation to the matrix component		
													preposition	Interposition	Postposition	Pre-postposition	Interposition	preposition	postposition
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
1.	<u>hindi</u>	+	4	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
2.	<u>persian</u>	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
3.	<u>pushtu</u>	+	5	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
4.	<u>kurd</u>	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
5.	<u>ossetian</u>	+	7	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
6.	<u>tat</u>	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
7.	<u>gillian</u>	+	5	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
8.	<u>yazgulem</u>	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
9.	<u>yahan</u>	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
10.	<u>shugnan</u>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
11.	<u>kachin</u>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
12.	<u>mundjan</u>	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
13.	<u>liy</u>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
14.	<u>lendi</u>	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
15.	<u>russian</u>	+	32	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
16.	<u>latish</u>	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+

17.	english	+	10	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
18.	freeze	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
19.	german	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
20.	italyian	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
21.	greek	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
22.	french	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
23.	latin	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
24.	arabic	+	5	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
25.	amhar	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
26.	akkad	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
27.	assirian	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
28.	samaritan	+	2	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
29.	syrian	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
30.	hausa	+	3	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	ss	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
31.	dargin	+	5	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	c	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
32.	abkhaz	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
33.	kabardin	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
34.	adigey	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
35.	kubachin.	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	-	-	+	-	-	-	+
36.	hungarian	+	5	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
37.	mansiy	+	2	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	c/w	-	+	-	-	-	-	+
38.	komi	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
39.	finn	+	5	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
40.	saam	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
41.	udmurt	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	-	+	+	-	+	-	-
42.	vepp	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
43.	turkish	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
44.	tatar	+	6	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c/w	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
45.	karach.balkar.	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	c	+	-	+	-	-	-	+
46.	karayim	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c/w	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
47.	uzbek	+	16	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
48.	kazakh	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	-	-	+	-	+	-	+
49.	karakalpak	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
50.	azarbajian.	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
51.	mongolian.	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	pp	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
52.	kaluyik	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	pp	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
53.	chinese	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	C	+	+	-	-	+	-	+

54.	dungan	+	6	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
55.	chjuan	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
56.	vietnamese	+	2	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
57.	birman	+	ss	ss	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	ss	-	-	-	-	-	-	ss
58.	tamil	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	c	-	-	+	-	+	-	-
59.	braui	+	4	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
60.	khmer	+	6	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
61.	indonezian	+	4	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
62.	buguix	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
												3							
63.	samoau	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
64.	maori	+	4	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
65.	tong	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
66.	minangkabau	+	5	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	ss	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
67.	havayi	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
68.	sundan	+	6	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
69.	ganda/luganda	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
70.	suahily	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
71.	taitian	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
72.	volof	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
73.	fula	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
74.	ruanda	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	+
75.	lingala	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
76.	malinke	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
77.	yoruba	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
78.	chukot	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
79.	koryak	+	1	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
80.	itelmen	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
81.	japanese	+	3	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
82.	eskimo.	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+
83.	tagal	+	4	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	c	+	-	-	-	-	-	+

(Table 2, compiled by us based on the analysis of the empirical material of the above languages, provides information on the presence of the HPT with AK of causality in the languages, while “+” means the presence of a feature(criterion), “numbers 1,2,3” – the quantity (number) of means of syntactic connections, “ss” – simple sentence (monotaxema) with adverbial modifier of causality, “+” – presence of feature(criterion), “-” – absence of feature(criterion), “c” – conjunction (dominant means of connection), “c/w” – the conjunctive word, “pp” – postposition, “pr” – preposition, “af” – affix, “p” – particle, “as” – asyndetic connection).

In such languages as Minangkabau, Hausa, a connection between the clauses of HPT and AC of causality is carried out by the subordinators represented only by conjunctive- prepositions, which indicates the member languages with the basic

word order of SVO, while in the Mongolian and Kalmyk languages, the subordinators are represented only by conjunctive-prepositions, which testifies to their typological structure with the typical order of the members of the sentence with the basic word order SOV. In other languages, there is the use of the subordinators represented by their composite type (consisting of more than one subordinator).

There are also such languages as Uzbek, Samaritan, Dargin, in which the subordinators, represented by connectors, are used along with conjunctions and postpositions, although the latter are not very frequent. There are also cases where, along with the syndetic connection, the asyndetic connection is also used. This is typical of languages such as Turkish, Karachay-Balkarian, etc. There are also cases of using the borrowed subordinators, which is not dominant in this regard. These are languages such as Indonesian, Sundanese, Eskimo, etc.

The quantitative characteristics of subordinators of causality used between the components of HPT with AC in languages is such that their number ranges from 1 to 6 or seven. At the same time, there are such languages as Tajik, Dungan and Sudanese using 6 types of subordinators, Ossetian - 7, languages like, Pashto, Gilyan, Dargin, Finnish, etc. have the number of subordinators ranging from 1 to 4.

As for English, there are all in all 10 subordinators of causality (such as “*because, since, so, that, lest, considering, for the reason that, in view of the fact that, in so far as, by reason of*”), in Russian - 32 (“*потому что, потому как, потому, так как, поскольку, раз, раз что, ибо, ведь, оттого что, из-за того что, ради того что, благодаря тому что, затем что, через то что, для того что, благо, как, вследствие того что, в результате того что, в силу того что, на основании того что, исходя из того что, по причине того что, по той причине что, в связи с тем что, ввиду того что, под видом того что, под предлогом того что, под тем предлогом что, тем более что, тем паче что*”),

and in Uzbek there are 16 subordinators of causality (such as “*chunki, negaki, nimagaki, sababi, sababki, shuning uchun, shu sababli, shuning uchun ... -ki, nega deng, nega desa (k/ng/ngiz/), nega deganda, nimag desa (k/ng/ngiz/), sabab desangiz, ...-ki, ... shekilli, ...-sa kerak, ...mi*”), including the borrowed ones.

Regarding the positional arrangement of subordinators, it can be noted that in languages there dominates the preposition of the subordinator in relation to the adverbial clause of causality. Out of the 83 languages that have HPT with AC of causality, in 73 of them the dominant position for the subordinator is the preposition, only in 7 languages the postposition of the subordinator dominates

and in 6 languages there is even an interposition dominant (in most cases, these are such languages as Finno-Ugric: Mansiy, Finnish, Komi, Saami, Udmurt, Vepps, etc. (see Table 2).

In languages also noteworthy is the positional arrangement of the adverbial clauses in relation to the matrix clause in the HPT with AC of causality. Thus, out of 83 languages subjected to the typological analysis, in 65 of them the adverbial clause occupies postposition. The preposition of the adverbial clause is observed in 17 languages out of the above given number. These are such languages as Kachin, Italian, Greek, Arabic, Dargin, Kazakh, Mongolian, Chinese, Dungan, Zhuang, Tamil, Indonesian, Minangkabau, Hawaiian, Lingala, Japanese and others.

Along with other positions, only 6 languages partially demonstrate interposition of the adverbial clause. These are languages like Ossetian, Gilyan, Yazgulyam, Wakhan, Frisian, Khmer, etc., although the subordinators themselves also impose restrictions on the freedom of the position of the clause, since with some subordinators the position of the adverbial clause is completely free (these are languages like Ossetian, where the subordinators, apparently originated from the classes of words with modal meanings).

Typological comparison of HPT with AC of causality in more than 80 concrete languages of the world listed in the above table allows us to formulate the following constant (universal, frequent and implicative) regularities(laws) of their structural-semantic organization and functional usage:

1) In the overwhelming majority of languages that have a hypotaxeme subsystem, there are HPT with AC of causality.

2) In the overwhelming majority of languages that have a HPT with AC of causality, conjunctors represented by conjunctions serve as means of syntactic connection between the adverbial clause and the center of subordination in the matrix clause.

3) In the overwhelming majority of languages, the AC of causality is located post-positionally in relation to the matrix clause of the hypotaxeme.

4) If a language has a HPT with AC of causality, then this language also has a monotaxeme with an adverbial modifier of causality.

5) If in a language that has a hypotaxeme, the original subordinator-conjunctor is in preposition in relation to the AC of causality, then in this language canonically the basic order is SVO (these are Indo-European languages: English, German, French, etc.).

6) If in a language that has a HPT subsystem with AC of causality, the primordial subordinator-conjunctor is in a postposition as to the non-matrix clause, then in this language the canonical basic word order is SOV. (these are Turkic-type of languages: Uzbek, Kazakh, Tuvan, Altai, Tatar, etc.).

7) If in a language that has a HPT with AC of causality, the original subordinator is in interposition as to the non-matrix clause, then in this language the canonical basic order is SOV /or OVS, or OSV/ (these are Turkic-type of languages: Uzbek, Kazakh, Tuvan, Altai, Tatar, etc.).

8) If in a language with a hypotaxeme, the original subordinator-conjunctor is in preposition as to the non-matrix clause, then in this language the non-matrix clause is canonically in post-position as to the matrix clause (these are the languages of the Indo-European type: English, German, French, Russian and etc.).

9) If in a language that has a HPT with AC of causality, the original subordinator-conjunctor is in postposition as to its non-matrix clause, then in this

language the non-matrix clause is canonically in preposition as to the matrix clause (these are Turkic-type of languages: Uzbek, Kazakh, Tuvan, Altai, Tatar, etc.).

10) If in a language that has a HPT with AC of causality, the original subordinator - conjunctive is in interposition as to its non-matrix clause, then the non-matrix clause is canonically in the preposition / or rarely in the interposition (these are Turkic-type of languages: Uzbek, Kazakh, Tuvan, Altai, Tatar, etc.).

11) If in a language that has HPT with AC of causality, the original subordinator is in postposition, then the subordinator is canonically in postposition in relation to its non-matrix clause, which itself has a strict preposition in relation to the matrix clause (these are Turkic-type of languages: Uzbek, Kazakh, Tuvan, Altai, Tatar, etc.).

12) If in a language that has a HPT with AC of causality, the original subordinators - conjunctives are synthetic means, then in this language the basic order is SOV and the order of the clauses are strict, and non-matrix clause itself is canonically in preposition as to the matrix clause (these are the Turkic-type of languages: Uzbek, Kazakh, Tuvan, Altai, Tatar, etc.).

13) If a language has a subsystem of a HPT with AC of causality, then in this language subordinators /conjunctives and connectors/, at least zero ones, serve as means of communication between its clauses.

Based on the foregoing, it can be summarized that in languages HPT with AC of causality constitute one of the frequently used types of polytaxemes, by the help of which universal causal relations are realized, although in languages such relations may also be expressed in their pure form by other syntactic means, namely, monotaxemes with an adverbial modifier, as well as other types of polytaxemes, phrasemes, etc., but causal relations expressed in such cases are often associated with other adjacent or close relations or semantics.

REFERENCES:

1. Khoshimov G.M. Typology of complex sentences in languages of different systems, Tashkent, "Fan", 1991, 107 p.;
2. Khoshimov G.M. .Typology of a complex sentence in non-related languages. Doctoral(Dsc) dissertation, Tashkent, 2002, pp. 121-136;
3. Khoshimov G.M.: Principles and methods of typological comparison of composite sentences, Andijzhan, "Khayot". 2017. 156 p.